

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B131
Date: 20 Sep 2005
Take Off: 10:27:23
Landing: 15:18:35
Flight Time: 4h51m12

Campaign: CLOPAP

Operating Area: Thames Estuary

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	Manchester University
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	CCN/CVI/CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
10	Noxy	Andy MacDonald	UEA
11	WAS	Debbie O'Sullivan	UEA
12	AMS	James Allen	Manchester University
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b131
 Date: 20 September 2005
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: Thames Estuary

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
100037		inu	0.03 kft	126	to navigate
100057		drs	0.03 kft	126	check - ok
102723		T/O	3.7 kft	027	Cranfield
103914		fl100	10.0 kft	064	calibration transit
105019		video	10.0 kft	072	ffc & rfc tape #1 started
105527		descending	9.3 kft	184	fl100 to above cloud top
105630	110432	Profile 1	7.9 - -.06 kft	182	
110042		nev zero	3.5 kft	183	
110556	111500	Run 1	0.19 - 0.18 kft	187	
111736	112235	Run 2	0.15 - 0.22 kft	316	
111857		bbr	0.19 kft	314	shutter open
112844	113532	Run 3	1.1 - 1.2 kft	315	
113708	114017	Run 4	0.72 - 0.75 kft	318	
114328	115543	Run 5	1.2 - 1.3 kft	153	1500ft
114443		bravo	1.3 kft	144	
115430		video	1.6 kft	104	ffc & rfc tape #2
115847	121117	Run 6	2.7 kft	321	3000ft
121554	122624	Run 7	1.7 kft	146	2000ft
123138	124259	Run 8	2.1 kft	329	2400ft
124644	125826	Run 9	1.2 kft	154	1500ft
130010		video	1.2 kft	052	ffc & rfc tape #3 started
130320	131537	Run 10	1.2 kft	330	1500ft
131945	133052	Run 11	2.5 kft	145	2800ft
133435	134636	Run 12	5.0 kft	331	fl150
135202	140204	Run 13	1.5 kft	148	1800ft
140304	141510	Run 14	0.70 - 0.72 kft	190	1000ft
140523		video	0.72 kft	192	ffc & rfc tapes #4 started
141600		FM PC	0.73 kft	002	froze and reset
141701	142336	Run 15	0.73 - 0.72 kft	359	1000f
142436	144259	Run 16	0.74 - 0.73 kft	017	
143515		manouvre	0.72 kft	036	change of heading 143403
144740		cals	10.0 kft	292	fl100
151835		Land	0.06 kft	309	Cranfield
152930		gps	0.06 kft	309	52'04.36N 0'37.50W
153039		inu	0.06 kft	309	52 04.26N 0 36.08W

B131 Track 20-SEP-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 8 (prepared by K.N. Bower)

Flight Number : B131

Date: Tuesday 20th September 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Aims:

To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol and gases with cloud both as the aerosol/gas modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol and gases.

CLOPAP Sortie Location:

The plan is to fly in an area of low cloud and sample pollution from a major urban area as it advects towards and interacts with the cloud layer. For this flight the option today is to sample the London plume E or NE of London in a W or SW in the Thames Estuary or off East Anglia (or in the Kent/English Channel area if the wind has a more northerly component). Low cloud is forecasted in this region and in the English Channel although winds are not forecasted to be very strong. In cloudy conditions, several sets of cross-wind runs of 12 minutes duration (or of half this duration on reciprocal headings) will be attempted at various altitudes in the time available. This may be adjusted by the mission scientist omitting parts of these sets of runs to best achieve the science goals in the conditions encountered. Current plans and flight level restrictions allow for three (Or four) sets of runs to be carried out consisting of up to four (or three) runs per set. Profiles will be carried out where possible in each set of runs

CLOPAP Sortie Summary:

The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of up to 84 km[#] transects across the plume within the boundary layer (one below cloud, and at least one in cloud) and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile (where possible) extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 25km[#] separation, to obtain up to 4 sets[#] of transects. Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advected downwind of the source region. Runs at each altitude may be cut down to a minimum total length of 12 minutes (or 84km) duration or omitted, or certain profiles sacrificed in order to achieve the required study of plume evolution and interaction with cloud. In the absence of cloud, fewer boundary layer transects will be performed, ie the “in-cloud” leg (and some profiles) will be omitted, and the spacing between sets of legs reduced so as to carry out more sets of runs (and hence improve detection of clear-air plume evolution) in the operational area.

CLOPAP Sortie Detail: PTO

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 8 (draft 1 : prepared by K.N. Bower/M.W.Gallagher)

Flight Number : B131

Date: Tuesday 20th September 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Detail:

1. Take off and climb to FL 100 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
2. When downwind of chosen urban source, descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform a profile ascent by climbing at 1000 ft per minute to pass through cloud and to an altitude 200 ft above cloud top/ boundary layer top.
3. Descend to below cloud base, proceed across wind in the boundary layer until outside the plume as detected by CN counter/gases. Mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform a straight and level run (SLR) below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind and of total length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should commence at the start of this run. Core Chemistry calibrations should be carried out at start of run (as required) and completion announced so that WAS sampling can begin.
4. Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Mission Scientist to announce in cloud transect (AMS to switch to CVI inlet) and perform SLR of length 84 km[#].
5. Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top turn through 180 degrees - mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect (AMS to return to Rosemount inlet). Perform a SLR of length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should also commence at the start of this run. In the event that we cannot operate above cloud top a second in-cloud run will be carried out at a higher altitude than in 4.
6. Ascend to cruising altitude to transit to 25[#] km downwind and repeat steps 2 to 6
7. Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted
8. Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)

NB. In the absence of cloud:

9. In the absence of cloud steps 3 and 4 will be replaced by a single in boundary layer cross-wind transect, and the transit distance between sets of runs in item 6 will be reduced to 25km to enable more sets of cross wind runs to be carried out.

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 8 (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : TWC/KNB

CLOPAP Scientific Aims

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected away from the source in cloudy conditions (if low cloud in this area)[#]. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

CLOPAP Weather Conditions

Ideally, a stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the sea downwind of a main source of urban air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

CLOPAP Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

Cloud Physics

- **FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP**, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high/low concentrations,
- **ADA and CPI** – as above
- **CCN** - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample and spectrum per run, if possible.
- **J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC**. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- **TWC** – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

WAS - 2 bottle samples per 84km flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist (first sample to be collected after core chemistry calibrations are completed).

NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.

AMS - to be operated on **Rosemount inlet** out of cloud, **CVI** inlet in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed or after take-off. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight or before landing.

Filters – these should be exposed on boundary layer out of cloud runs.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rearward facing.

CCN measurements :alleviator should be filled at the start of cloud free passes.

Bottle filling and filter sampling should occur in clear air transects only. Two[#] bottle samples should be filled during each boundary layer transect and 1 during the free troposphere transect. The Mission scientist will indicate when in plume using CN and selected gas measurements. All other instruments should run continuously.

Sortie de-brief: CLOPAP 8

Flight Number: B131
Date: 20th September 05
M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol and gases with cloud both as the aerosol/gas modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol and gases.

Sortie Location:

In the London plume in an area of low cloud to the E and NE of London in the Thames estuary and over Norfolk.

Weather conditions:

A low pressure system situated to the north of the British Isles over night moved eastwards towards Scandinavia during the day causing a series of weak fronts to travel NW to SE across the UK. A weak trailing frontal system consisting of a warm front closely followed by a cold front moved south-eastwards across the country during the morning, and this was quickly followed by another cold front/occluded front which was forecasted to be situated over the SE of the country by midday.

Met Office mesoscale model output (00:00z model run)

Whilst expected to be weakening and producing little in the way of precipitation, these fronts were expected to bring low cloud to the East Anglia, Thames estuary and Kent region during the midday to mid afternoon period. However, winds were forecasted to be very light, around 5 knots or less, and consequently predicted wind direction (from different models) varied from being westerly to south-westerly or southerly as the isobars separated and organised flow diminished.

Flight Summary

Following takeoff at 10:27:21z a NO_x calibration was carried out during transit at FL100 to point 40 off the NE coast of East Anglia. After descending to 8000ft, a profile descent P1 to 250ft asl was carried out following a right hand turn onto a heading of 182°. During P1, cloud top (CT) was seen at around 3500ft and cloud base (CB) around 3000ft, although both CT and CB were very variable in the region. Some broken clouds were seen below with tops at around 2300ft, and at around this level PCASP reported a huge spike in concentration. Once in the BL, CO, NO_x and CN increased substantially, at low level towards the end of P1. The valve on the filters was opened at the end of P1. SO₂ levels also increased at the start of Run 1, a run carried out at 500ft parallel to the Norfolk coast tracking south from point 40 towards point 41. AMS reported seeing observable loadings on the normal logging screen. SO₂, NO_x and CN levels started to fall away after 2-3 minutes of R1 (having peaked at around 5ppb, 20ppb and 20,000 cm⁻³ respectively), although CO remained elevated. Winds were light at around 5m/s, and 255°. R1 was continued on beyond point 41 until reaching the point of intersection with the extrapolated line B-A (in the outer Thames estuary) at 11:15:05.

The plume of NO_x, SO₂ and CN increased again at the end of R1 and start of R2, another run at 500ft back towards A. In the estuary, winds were again around 5m/s but on a heading of 240-250°. Concentrations of gases and particles decreased after the start of R2. The run was continued on beyond point A to get closer in to the coast. At this point cloud was seen above, and so it was decided to turn and ascend to 1500ft to head back to A and then do a first cross-wind run below cloud (mostly over land) back from point A to point B. On this run, R3, the wind was very light (4m/s or less) and it generally had a more northerly component (between 260-290°). The plume in NO_x and CN was again observed along with a rise in CO, but peak loadings were

reduced to around 8ppb and 6000-7000 cm⁻³ respectively. Only a small rise in SO₂ (to 0.5ppb) above background was detected. Ozone and NO_x appeared to be anti-correlated. Towards the end of this transect cloud was encountered and so R3 was terminated and the transect completed as R4 at 1000ft. After turning, it was decided to do the reciprocal transect B-A (R5) in cloud at 1500ft. At 11:41z, the AMS was switched onto the CVI inlet, and the filters valve was closed. At the start of R5 cloud was quite thin and patchy, and cloud droplets were small as they were seen by the FSSP probe, but not by the 2D probes (the CPI was operating without a rack operator). At 11:48 rain was visible on the aircraft windscreen and by the 2D probes. Within a minute R5 was into a CB region and then into cloud free air. A sharp rise in NO_x from 1 to 20ppb was observed, along with a slight rise in SO₂ and a 50% rise in CN. The PCASP concentration was described as “rocketing up”. At this point it was realised the CVI had not been turned on, so the AMS was returned to the Rosemount inlet (11:53z). The CVI was prepared for the next in-cloud pass.

Run 6 was carried out on a reciprocal transect A-B at 3000ft, above the tops of cloud where NO_x, SO₂ and CN concentrations were at detection limits for gases and less than 1000cm⁻³ for particles. O₃ was at its highest (>40ppb) since the transit leg. 8.5 minutes into R6, the aircraft encountered general CT and the tops of some small turrets, which coincided with a huge spike in CPC (inlet related?) and a small spike in NO_x. CO was also observed to be varying in the convective CT regions during descent at the end of R6. The CVI was reported as working and so it was decided to do the reciprocal run B-A in cloud. The AMS was changed to the CVI inlet (at 12:14:25z) and R7 commenced at 2000ft. NO_x started creeping up a little (filters were off) and after 3-4 minutes the aircraft flew in and out of cloud. At this level the wind was around 5 m/s and 250-260°. After 12:21 R7 was out of cloud, and the filters inlet was opened. NO_x spiked to 5ppb, O₃ increased as CO decreased, and CN increased to as high as 8000-9000 cm⁻³. A haze layer was seen below the aircraft, and above some cloud was observed.

The aircraft ascended to transit at 2400ft to point C to start the middle set of cross-wind transects. With the AMS still on the CVI, the AMS CPC was seeing counts while the CVI CNC saw no counts. R8 going from C-D at 2400ft started out of cloud and then encountered cloud after 4 minutes. The cloud was broken, and again the CPC saw spikes as cloud edges were encountered. At 12:42:10z the FSSP was reported as having crashed but was rebooted by 12:42:54z, the end of R8. During R8 winds were light (~3m/s) and generally westerly with a slight northerly component (~270-280°). The reciprocal leg D-C, R9, was carried out below cloud at 1500ft and encountered a broad plume with a moderate level of pollution throughout (NO_x ≤5ppb, CN ~5000cm⁻³ (⊕2500) although CPC=3000⊕1000cm⁻³, and CO again elevated >1500ppb). A larger spike in NO_x was observed near the end of R9, but SO₂ remained low (<0.5ppb) throughout R9. The AMS was switched back to the Rosemount inlet at the start of the run (at 12:46z) (and the filter valve opened). Ozone was again anti-correlated with NO_x. During R9 winds were slightly stronger (4-6m/s) with a larger northerly component (~280-300°). The plume edge was encountered at the very end of R9 (NO_x, CN and CO dropped, O₃ increased)

The aircraft transited at 1500ft from C to E to begin the final set of crosswind transects. R10 going from E-F at 1500ft below cloud encountered a similar broad plume to that seen in R9 (elevated NO_x, CN, and slightly elevated CO, reduced O₃)

although peak concentrations were slightly lower in comparison. Between 13:05:30z and 13:07:45z the aircraft flew through a layer of haze. PCASP concentrations increased from around 600 to ~2000cm⁻³, but this was not seen by the FSSP. The reciprocal transect (R11) was carried out at 2800ft in cloud. The AMS switched to sampling off the CVI inlet at 13:16z, with the CPC seeing ~600cm⁻³ (?). At this altitude the wind was around 5-6m/s and 300-330°, but smoke from stubble burning on the ground indicated that the surface wind seemed to be directly across our track. The cloud disappeared right at the end of R11, and the AMS was returned to the Rosemount inlet (13:30z) and the filter valve opened. Although O₃ concentration gradually increased across R11, NO_x and CN levels remained similar to those on the below cloud transect. The reciprocal above cloud leg E-F (R12) was carried out at 5000ft well above cloud and the BL. Unsurprisingly, CN and CO concentrations dropped right down to background values (1500-2500cm⁻³ and ~100ppb), while NO_x and SO₂ were at/near their detection limits (effectively 0ppb).

During descent (between F and E) CT and CB were seen to be around 2850 and 2150ft respectively (NB the filter inlet was not closed and AMS not switched to CVI inlet during descent). As soon as the BL was encountered CO, NO_x, CN and PCASP concentrations increased. A final crosswind below cloud leg (R13) at 1800ft was carried out going from D to C. Plume concentrations were similar to those in R9. PCASP reported the lowest concentrations for some time. However, at the end of R13 the aircraft turned right and descended to 1000ft to carry out a cross estuary leg heading for point 42. During this manoeuvre, a thick haze layer was encountered and PCASP concentrations rocketed. A huge spike in SO₂, NO_x, CN (and decrease in O₃) was observed 5.5 minutes into R14 (~14:08:32z) (7ppb, 33ppb, 22000cm⁻³ and 27ppb respectively) and the captain reported a region of good visibility. Winds at this level were ~4m/s and 250°. R14 was stopped at point 42, and the aircraft made a right turn to return initially on a reciprocal to R14 – but closer in to the Kent coast, turning left at the north-eastern tip of the county to travel further into the estuary before turning right to carry out a run (R16) parallel to the track of R14. During the early part of R15 (between point 42 and the turn to start R16) off the east coast of Kent, the AMS recorded loadings of the order of µg. Levels of NO_x, SO₂ and CN shot up as a power station and another industrial building was passed on the coast on the LHS. During the last cross estuary transect (R16) the winds were light 2-3m/s and almost from due west (~275°). The huge plume was again picked up mid-run. Upon reaching the intersection with the track of the initial middle set of cross wind transects (C-D), R16 was continued on as the aircraft flew around the S and E coast of East Anglia at 1000ft. The original plume (smaller than the estuary plume) was encountered again in this leg. Upon reaching Lowestoft, R16 was terminated and the aircraft turned left and ascended to FL100 for the transit home and NO_x calibration .

A further run by run pictorial summary of the flight may be obtained from the mission scientists powerpoint file of screen dumps from flight B131.

Mission Scientist's Log

MSCI KEITH BOWER

CLOPATO 3

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/09/05**.....

Page **1** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:27:21	BST				T/D
11:30:20		4000'			some tiny puffs of cloud below ~ 3000'
		5000'			above adjacent CB (~ 4700)
		6000'			in broken cloud
		7100'			CT (Captain → CT FL 65-70)
11:36:00	NO ₂ s	FL100			NO ₂ Cal.
10:49:50	NO ₂ s	FL600	72	52.7N/1.3E	1.31°/-29.7°C 4m/s/281° 696mb 249kts
10:51:59		FL100	72	52.7/1.6E	Over Coast of East Angles
11:53:00	NO ₂ s	FL100	72	52.6/1.7E	NO ₂ Cal complete 0.34°/-12.28° a.m.s/216°
10:54:50	descending				Will profile from above CT.
10:56:25	P1 st	FL60	162	52.6/1.8E	
10:57:19	P1	FL70	163	52.5/1.8E	4.12°/1.56°C 2m/s/255° 761mb 236kts
10:58:00	P1	6200			Some cloud here.
11:00:59	P1	3500			CT 3500
11:01:20		3000			CB
11:01:36	P1	2600	164	52.2/1.7E	CT
	P1	2300			above CT now.
					cloud is quite thin with lots below/a
11:02:56					huge spike in PLASP
11:03:26					W 11kts
					CO ↑ NO ₂ Core Chem
					ONC 39000
11:03		500'			NO ₂ spike
11:04:32	P1 end	250'			Filters - open valves
11:05:57	P1 st	500'	167	52.0/1.7E	

Mission Scientist's Log

MSCI KEITH BOWEN

CLOPAP 8

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/09/05**.....

Page **2** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					AMS seeing brookings on loggers ocean
11:09:00	R1	500'	187	51.4/1.7E	CO cont complete
11:11:09					NO ₂ SO ₂ falling a little now, CN too
11:11:54					CO high - 134 ppb
					NO ₂ - sun plume - falling off
					CO rising again - all other conc down
11:15:05	R1 end	500'			CO ↓ dropped - now rising
11:17:34	R2 st	500	315	51.5/1.5E	Wind Smls/223° 1007 mb 218 kts 14.64/10.7°C
11:20:27	R2	500	312	51.6/1.3E	passing A Smls/245 CO was dropping
					putting up again, NO ₂ being seen
11:22:33	R2 end	500	315	51.7/1.2E	Cloud ahead also
					CO at highest ~ 200 ppb - falling now
					to 185 - Alt - climbing to 1500'
11:24:46		1500			Going to point A to do 1 st below deck
					run over land.
11:28:43	R3 st	1500	311	51.6/1.3E	heading towards coast
11:29:30					
					CO - step rise NO ₂ is up rising - CO
11:31:00	R3	1500			down. SO ₂ 0.47, NO ₂ 8.33 ppb CN 0000
					OPC - 3500 / m ² CNC 12000
11:32:23	R3	1500	318	51.8/1.1E	PCASP, CO dropping reach 180 ppb
					NO ₂ level 19 ppb
11:33:24					CO, NO ₂ ↑ ↑
				51.9/0.9	
					CO ↑ NO ₂ ↑

Mission Scientist's Log

M SCI

KEITH BOWER

0207108

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/09/05**.....

Page **3** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:35:30	R3 end	1500	316	52.0/0.8F	OB dropping
11:37:08	44 st	1000'	323	52.1/0.7F	2D - rain, (10 miles b run) 137mb
			323		1m/s/269° 986 mb, NO ₂ ↑ CO ↑
11:40:15	R4 end	1000'	323	52.2/0.6	AMS → CVI - filter shut
		1500'			
11:43:26	R5 st	1500	160	52.2/0.6F	969mb 12.87°/11.33 undant temp/305
11:44:30	RS	1500	140	52.1/0.7	another start down - thin dust - point B
11:45:31	RS	1500			Broken dust r below safety altitude. !!!
11:46:16	RS	1500	142	52.0/0.8F	in CT - now back in dust again
					2D - small patches - not seen on 2D probe
11:47:45					just FSSP - now 2D says it
11:48:15	RS	1500	141	51.9/0.9F	Rain on Windscreen - 2D to.
11:49:18	RS	1500	142	51.9/0.9F	in CB here
11:50:14					CO, NO ₂ ↑ out of dust.
					PCASP rocket up - CO ₂
					AMS - some shut on CVI -
	ARR RHH !!!				NO CVI - BUOBER - AMS → Reset.
11:55:42	RS end	1500	141	51.6/1.4E	
11:54:47	R6 st	3000'			
12:00:57	R6	3000	320	51.6/1.3F	10.23°/8.64° (240/7HL Waltham)
12:01:50	R6	3000	320	51.7/1.2E	2mb/28°, Core Chem cal dem 918mb.
12:03:32					Core Chem all gone - O ₃ 400mb 10 1000mb all gases v. dem

Mission Scientist's Log

M SCI

KEITH BOWER

CLOPPS

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/9/09**.....

Page **4** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:06:19	R6	3000	320	51.9/0.9F	In cloud tops - and out - CO in AMS - by spike CPC
12:09:30					OVI now within
12:11:11	R6 on	3000		52.1/0.6	
12:12:20					Photo LMS, AMS, of CT
					Will do next run in cloud - AMS on CM
12:13:54				51.1/0.5	On track.
12:14:25					on OVI inlet
12:14:45	2500				CO very in in cumulative dark
12:15:52	R7 ↓	2000'	139.	52.1/0.7F	AMS - 10s / cm ³ 50 or so
		2000	140	52.0/0.7F	11.91/10.75°C 3m/s/267° 952mb 216kts
12:18:40	R7	2000	140	51.9/0.9.	NO ₂ coming up again (D in cal mode) (Filters are dr.) In and out of cloud
12:21:14	R7	2000	142	51.8/1.0.	now out of cloud
					NO ₂ - spike ~ Spob. O ₃ ↑ as CO ₂
					CN ↑ - out of cloud - open filter
12:24:15h					AMS CPC - ~ 10-11 cm ⁻³
					Photo AMS - haze below cloud above
12:25:50					Peak of CO after 5s - spike in PCMS
					NO ₂ ↑ 10 sat, 2D
12:26:22	R7end	2000		51.6/1.3E	CO background now.
12:29:52	trans	2400'	42	51.7/1.6E	level - core chemicals
					CM1 CPC - no cond, AMS CPC - seeing cond
12:31:36	R8 st	2400'	323'	51.8/1.6E	
					Gas over Felixstowe estuary - in cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

M SCI

ICETH BOWEN

CLOPAPS

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/09/08**.....

Page **5** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:35:40	R8	2400	321	52.0/1.4E	In cloud - gaps in den Deben - river - in and out over Woodbrook
12:39:05	R8	2400	321	52.1/1.2	AMS - spikes in CPC - will be dead
12:42:10	R8	2400	321	52.3/1.0E	FSSP frozen - will reboot
12:42:34	R8 end	2400	-	52.3/1.0	FSSP rebooted
12:46:43	R1st	1500	142	52.3/1.0	Below den - run Molecular pollution NO _x 3.9 ppb CN 4500 cm ⁻³ SO ₂ 0.37 Downwind of Ahlstrom/Hammish
12:57:12					NO _x starting up 91, SO ₂ 0.27 - Spikes NO _x CN ~ 4000-6000 cm ⁻³ CPC ~ 2-4000
12:58:21	R9 end	1500	5	51.7/1.7E	12.52/10.6' 969mb 7m/s/500' 204kt
13:03:14	R10st	1500	321	51.9/2.0E	12.95/10.42' 969mb 2m/s/307' 200kt CO on way back up - NO _x too - just CN increasing too - CO now
13:05:30	R10			52.0/1.8	PCASP - gone up last min 600 → 2000 - in haze - FSSP not seen much
				52.1/	NO _x ↑, CN ↑ (CO ~ 125 ppb)
13:07:45	R10	1500			Clear of haze - PCASP in near for haze low
13:08:45	R10			52.1/1.7E	CO NO _x ↑, wind 2m/s/277, Cst 267, Co 274
13:10:21	R10	1500	322	52.2/1.6E	Crossing Cond CO rising slowly - NO _x - gone up, CN ↑
13:15:36	R10 end	1500		52.5/1.2E	
13:19:47	R11st	2800	146	52.4/1.3E	10.51/10.69' 922mb 213kt 3m/s/324kt

Mission Scientist's Log

M SCI KEITH BOWER

CLOPAB

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date **20/01/05**.....

Page **6** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:21:14	R11	2500	146	52.4/19.4E	AMS - CVI mlt - 600 cm ³
					only started seeing patches at this level
					ste wind is across us on ground - stable burning
13:24:40	R11	2500	142	51.9/19E	AMS → Rosemont, Filters on again
13:30:47	R11 end	2500	142	51.9/20E	
13:37:38			↻		3 photos - On RMS - looking back at CT's
13:34:17	R12 st	5000	331	51.9/20E	
13:48:20					CT ~ 2850 CB ~ 2150
					CO ↑ NO ₂ ↑ PCASP ↑
13:50:06	R12 end	5000			
13:51:09	R13 st	1500	145	52.2/1.1E	Filters on, AMS still on Rosemont, (CN scrub)
					2D - PCASP lowest A _e for long time
14:02:00	R13 end	1500	↻	51.7/1.7E	2D - PCASP - rocketed up - deep in haze layer
14:03:03	R14 st	1000	141	51.7/1.6E	
14:09:32	R14	1000	140	51.3/1.5E	huge spike in SO ₂ , NO ₂ , CN
					O ₃ now ↑
14:12:30	R14	1000	140	51.2/1.5E	O ₃ dropping again - as are all others
					Good visibility here
14:14:03	R14				Sharp rise in NO ₂ O ₃ dropped SO ₂
14:15:08	R14c	1000		51.0/1.5E	RMT
14:16:51	R15 s	1000			CEN sample
					AMS - order of mg - again all v same
14:16:28		1000		51.2/1.4E	NO ₂ ↑ SO ₂ ↑ CN ↑
					power str. of to LMS ?? + other molecules

→
(13:46:36)
R12 end

-

Mission Scientist's Log

M SCI KEITH BOWEN

CLOPPAS

Flight No **B.131**.....

Date 20/09/05.....

Page 7 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CO had dropped down - now rising back up as is NO ₂ , SO ₂
14:23:31	R15 end	1000		51.3/1.2E	
14:24:23	R16 st	1000	19	51.4/1.2E	- Not much cloud above CO dropped - now ↑ again
14:27:56					CO pushing up again - NO _x ↑
14:28:59	R16	1000	9	51.6/1.3E	14.6/11.55° 3m/s/272° 986mb 207kt
14:31:02	R16			51.7/1.4	CO at background NO _x etc fallen CO, NO _x ↑ again good vis to West, poor vis to N.
14:33:48	R16				1m/s/255
14:34:03	R16 B	1000	38		turn.
14:35:13	R16 B				Sharp increase in CO. ON ↑ NO _x too small inc in SO ₂
14:40	R16 B	1000	11	52.3/1.7E	Thick cloud above 986mb, 0m/s/181° 15.07/1.7E
14:42:57	R16 e	1000	5	52.4/1.7E	0m/s/247 14.7/12.5° 97 LMT and ascending.
14:46:32	NO ₂ s	FL100			NO ₂ s Calc
15:04:12	NO ₂ s	FL100	246	52.4/0.2E	NO ₂ s Calc complete 0.44°/-20.26° 8m/s/247° 696mb 235kt
16:19:30	B57				landing

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B131
Date : 20 Sept 2005
Operator & contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	None
TDLAS	Not fitted
WAS	None notified

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
 Shorter (quick cals) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
10:35:30 – 10:37	FL100	Bad cal – cal gas pressure low
10:40:22	FL100	Redone with full cal gas pressure – sensitivity low
10:45:02	FL100	Sensitivity still a little low
10:51:51	FL100	
11:08:54	500'	
11:27:51	1500'	
11:37:30 – 11:38:00	700'	Quick cal valve check – no full cal. required.
11:45:11	1500'	
12:01:28	3000'	
12:19:01	2000'	
12:33:00	2400'	
12:49:20	1500'	
13:22:55	2800'	
13:36:25	FL050	
13:51:30 – 13:51:45	200'	Aborted due to change of altitude
13:54:54	1800'	
14:06:10	1000'	
14:51:18	FL100	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B131

Date: 20/08/05

Operator:JT

Page1 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
				Not requested							SID not requested
											DAU 1 15 seconds slow
10:56:24	258	0.06	17		0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile 1 descent 8000ft
10:57:57	189	0.06	17		0	0	0	0	0	0	7000ft
10:58:13	39	0.07	19		0	0	0	0	0	0	6000ft
10:59:10	41	0.07	19		0	0	0	0	0	0	5000ft
11:00:10	050	0.06	19		0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft
11:01:10	58	0.08	21		0	0	0	0	0	0	3000ft / 35000ft cloud top
11:02:04	302	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	2000ft
11:03:01	1054	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	1000ft
11:03:31	1509	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	500ft
11:04:00	1547	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	250ft – end of profile 1
11:05:55	1279	0.09	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 1 500ft
11:07:00	1243	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:09:00	1576	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:11:00	1067	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:13:00	884	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:15:00	1255	0.07	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 1
11:17:35	836	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 2 500ft
11:19:00	1371	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:21:00	1180	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:22:34	1416	0.09	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 2
11:28:44	507	0.07	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 3 1500ft
11:30:00	1156	0.08	37		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:32:00	1570	0.08	38		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of large spike approx 2000
11:34:00	962	0.07	38		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:35:40	947	0.08	43		0	0	0	0	00	0	End run 3 to drop out of cloud
11:37:08	907	0.08	47		0	0	0	2008	400	1	Start run 4 1000ft
11:39:00	854	0.08	47		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:40:15	855	0.08	47		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 4
11:43:26	943	0.09	53		0-	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 5 1500ft
11:45:00	382	0.06	84		0	0	0	0	0	0	Broken cloud leg

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B130

Date: 20/09/05

Operator: JT

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:47:00	284	0.07	224		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:49:00	963	0.07	240		0	0	0	0	0	0	Passed through rain
11:51:00	2095	0.07	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:53:00	1593	0.08	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:55:41	1675	0.08	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 5
11:58:48	259	0.06	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 6 3000ft
12:00:00	71	0.06	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:02:00	73	0.06	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:04:00	36	0.06	241		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:06:00	438	0.2	402		0	0	0	0	0	0	Went through cloud little rain
12:08:00	71	0.07	419		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:10:00	101	0.06	419		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:11:13	101	0.06	419		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 6
12:15:55	351	0.09	744		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 7 2000ft
12:17:00	467	0.07	800		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:19:00	158	0.07	839		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:21:00	774	0.08	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:23:00	213	0.06	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:25:00	1431	0.09	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:26:24	089	0.07	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 7
12:31:37	110	0.06	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 8 2400ft
12:33:00	150	0.07	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:35:00	272	0.07	944		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:37:00	19	0.06	1022		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:39:00	671	0.1	1022		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:41:00	323	0.17	1022		0	0	0	0	0	0	FFSSP restarted after freeze
12:42:59	362	0.23	170		0	0	0	25	200	1	End of run 8
12:46:44	550	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 9 1500ft
12:48:00	744	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:50:00	565	0.08	443		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:52:00	620	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:54:00	348	0.07	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B130

Date:20/09/05

Operator: JT

Page 3 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:56:00	543	0.07	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:58:00	674	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:58:19	734	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 9
13:03:17	620	0.07	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 10 1500ft
13:05:00	1443	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:07:00	1421	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:09:00	1024	0.07	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:11:00	1033	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:13:00	646	0.08	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:15:00	852	0.09	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:15:36	1054	0.09	432		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 10
13:19:40	788	0.09	436		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 11 2800ft
13:21:00	526	0.09	587		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:23:00	456	0.12	754		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:25:00	472	0.15	971		0	0	0	66	200	1	
13:27:00	40	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:29:00	35	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:30:48	40	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 11
13:34:20	36	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 12 5000ft
13:36:00	46	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:38:00											
13:42:00	457	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:44:00	25	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:46:29	51	0.06	990		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 12
13:51:59	821	0.09	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 13 1800ft
13:53:00	795	0.09	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:55:00	869	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:57:00	1226	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:59:00	974	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	00	
14:01:00	1040	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:02:00	514	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 13
14:03:04	1529	0.08	1027		0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 14 1000ft

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
					1	2	3	4	5	
142635		142708	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.39	0.47	0.68	1.04	1.33	1.94	S
				26.50	1274	1277	1925	2343	3000	D
				26.44	268	268	268	274	279	B
				26.54	2282	2268	2267	2253	224	R
				26.13	1022.3	1022.3	1022.4	1022.4	1022.4	P
143921		143953	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.29	0.47	0.68	1.07	1.32		S
				26.51	1123	1505	2188	2572		D
				26.60	200	304	513	503		B
				26.43	2240	2234	2226	2221		R
					1022.3	1022.3	1022.4	1022.4		P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
										S
										D
										B
										R
										P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
										S
										D
										B
										R
										P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
										S
										D
										B
										R
										P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
										S
										D
										B
										R
										P

Change
height

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
					1	2	3	4	5	
111745	111818		500 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	RUN 1
				25.20	0.67	0.68	1.09			S
				25.0	70	74	39			D
				25.09	161	148	118			B
				25.05	2212	2223	2248			R
				24.98	1023.7	1023.7	1023.7			P
112834	112921		1500 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	RUN 2
				25.80	0.47	0.69	1.04	1.34	1.99	S
				25.89	2043	2201	3637	3795	4092	D
				25.55	701	702	709	709	701	B
				25	2319	2321	2325	2321	2326	R
				25	1024.0	1024.1	1023.7	1023.7	1023.7	P
124720	124755		1500 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.40	0.46	0.67	1.07	1.31	1.91	S
				26.32	1464	1832	1924	2934	3065	D
				26.26	711	699	695	690	746	B
				26.12	2323	2326	2321	2320	2316	R
				25.94	1022.8	1022.8	1023.0	1023.0	1023	P
125330	125801		1500 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.34	0.47	0.69	1.03	1.35	1.94	S
				26.21	1795	1951	2457	2715	3609	D
				26.08	709	700	700	702	704	B
				26.02	2323	2320	2317	2311	2305	R
				26.01	1023.0	1023.0	1023.0	1023.0	1023	P
130345	130414		1500 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.15	0.47	0.67	1.02	1.24	1.95	S
				26.10	1324	2181	2571	3087	3240	D
				26.08	739	735	731	736	726	B
				26.02	2309	2307	2302	2289	2288	R
				25.98	1022.9	1023.0	1022.8	1022.8	1022	P
135230	135320		1800		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.38	0.45	0.68	1.03	1.33	1.94	S
				26.32	495	659	1857	2449	2325	D
				26.30	390	381	383	391	392	B
				26.26	2350	2338	2301	2332	2332	R
				26.21	1022.3	1022.3	1022.4	1022.4	1022.4	P
140309	140341		1000 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.34	0.43	0.66	1.01	1.32	1.91	S
				26.31	2030	1734	2919	2095	4010	D
				26.24	365	364	375	376	380	B
				26.26	2335	2332	2322	2321	2317	R
				26.14	1022.4	1022.4	1022.3	1022.2	1022.3	P
141708	141741		1000 ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				26.14	0.46	0.68	1.02	1.34	1.91	S
				26.10	1793	2657	2891	3489	5707	D
				26.05	333	320	311	312	310	B
				26.01	2308	2301	2292	2285	2280	R
				26.00	1022.0	1022.4	1022.4	1022.3	1022.4	P

Bored

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B131.....

Date: 2019/05

Campaign Name: CLOPAP.....

Operator: DESAIE OSULU VAN

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		Argon Cylinder = 150 bar WAS Cylinder = 55 bar Time check at 10:08:30 Z Cases 7, 5 and 1 available 31 bottles	
N 10:54		Profile 1 started at FL 80	
11:05:56		Run 1 at 500 ft	
11:10:12	1	in plume	3.35
11:15:00		end of Run 1	
11:17:36		start of Run 2 @ 500ft towards A	
11:20:26		just passing point A	
11:21:39	2	in plume	3.36
11:22:35		end of Run 2	
11:28:44		start of Run 3 at 1500 ft from A	
11:30:37	3	over sea in plume	3.32
11:33:27	4	over land in plume	3.32
11:35:33		end of Run 3, descending	
11:37:10		Run 4 at 1000 ft	
11:40:		end of Run 4	
11:43:28		start of Run 5 at 1500 ft - in cloud Run	
11:50:04	5	CO + NOx increasing	3.32
11:51:41	6	in plume	3.32
11:55:43		end of Run 5, ascending	

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B131.....

Date: 20/9/05.....

Campaign Name: CLOPAP.....

Operator: DEBIE.....

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
11:58:47		Start of Run 6 at 3000 ft	
12:03:28	7	Clean background air above cloud	3.27
12:11:17		end of Run 6	
12:15:54		Run 7 at 2000 ft in cloud	
12:26:08	8		3.30
12:26:24		End of Run 7	
12:31:38		Start of Run 8 at 2400 ft -> middle transect in cloud Run	
12:42:59		end of Run 8	
12:46:44		Start of Run 9 at 1500 ft out of cloud	
12:50:10	9	In London Plume	3.31
12:53:30	10		3.31
12:58:26		end of Run 9	
13:03:20		Start of Run 10 at 1500 ft - last transect.	
13:04:26	11	CO↑ NOx↑ in Haze	3.31
13:12:07	12	" "	3.31
13:15:37		end of Run 10 at 1500 ft	
13:19:45		Start of Run 11 at 2800 ft - in cloud Run last transect.	
13:23:22	13		3.29
13:28:56	14		3.28
13:30:52		end of Run 11 at 2800 ft	

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: .B131.....

Date: 20.12.05...

Campaign Name: ...CLOPPA.....

Operator: DEBBIE.....

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
13:34:25		Run 12 FL 50	
13:37:46	15		3.19
13:46:36		end of Run 12	
13:52:02		Start of Run 13 at 1800 ft	
13:55:08	25		3.50
		towards point C (from D) middle transect	
14:02:04		end of Run 13 at 1800 ft	
14:03:04		start of Run 14 at 1000 ft	
14:06:57	26	Haze	3.32
14:13:24	27	↑ CO, NOx	3.32
14:15:08		end of Run 14 at 1000 ft	
14:16:56		Start of Run 15 at 1000 ft	
14:18:52	28	↑ CO, NOx	3.32
14:23:34	29	"	3.32
14:23:36		end of Run 15 at 1000 ft	
14:24:36		Start of Run 16 at 1000 ft	
14:28:29	30	↑↑ CO, NOx	3.32
14:33:50	31	estuary area.	3.32
14:42:59	32	end of 16 at 1000 ft	
14:47:08	32		3.04

used 23 bottles (8 bottles left - case 1)

BIBI JAMES 20/9/5

INLET SWITCHES

TIME	ROSEMOUNT	CVI	CVI NOT RUNNING
11:41	✓	✓	
11:53	✓		
12:15 (ish)		✓	
12:46	✓		
13:16		✓	
13:30	✓		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 131

Date: 20 September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		n
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		n
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		N
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		n			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red		Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon		Y			
“ JO1D		Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP		N
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon		Y	Filters		Y
“ JO1D		Y	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		Y
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		Y
NOX		Y	ADA		Y
CO		Y	CPI		Y
ORAC		N	NOxy		Y
PAN		Y	PTRMS		n
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling		n
WAS		Y	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B131

Date: 20 September 2005

Instruments

- 1 TWC not fitted
- 2 FM's pc froze – rebooted ok
- 3 T/O vibration strongly evident as striations on FFC, some still seen in climb and cruise –Avalon investigating in case of loose connection
- 4 ARINC 429 pressure displayed as 1013 & 0kft despite rebooting port aft dlu. Ok in flight

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls nil